

Contractual autonomy and new green economy

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1. Legal instruments for programming the new green economy

The first phase concerns the choice of the legal instruments for programming the new green economy.

The European Commission with the New Green Deal identifies ambitious climate goals (achieving climate neutrality) for the next few years (by 2050), under the banner of economic, social and environmental sustainability.

European policy intends to program interventions with a plurality of legal instruments (sources), which can essentially be distinguished according to whether they are authoritative or conventional.

The authoritative sources are mainly legislative sources, European and state, which impose in a binding way the objectives and the actions to be carried out, both on public administrations, businesses and citizens. Authoritative sources are an important lever, but not sufficient, because they are too rigid and limited in scope.

The Commission itself foresees a wide use of conventional instruments, both to coordinate the various European, national and regional public administrations and to develop more appropriate solutions to the various intervention contexts. We want to foster extensive collaboration and sharing both within the European Union and with other external institutions, the United Nations and non-EU states, with which to sign international agreements.

Moreover, the conventional instrument is also hypothesized to involve private stakeholders, to be included and encouraged in the transition processes to the new green economy.

Summary: internal and international, public and private agreements for the green economy are a second strategic lever for change that really wants to be shared and implemented by all, both those who are advantaged and those who may be affected by prejudices.

Agreements, therefore, are the tool for a transformation that is inclusive, an indispensable premise of the feasibility of the transformation objectives.

2. Legal instruments for implementing the new green economy

The second phase concerns the legal instruments for implementing the new green economy.

The objectives set in the legal sources need to be implemented in the various contexts, both by public administrations and by individuals, businesses and citizens.

Once again, European programs can be implemented coercively with administrative tools by European and national institutions. These implementation tools are important but not sufficient, as they have a limited scope for public intervention. It is also essential to involve private individuals, both for aspects concerning relations with the public administration and relations between private individuals.

Again, conventional tools are indispensable for the implementation of green economy actions.

On the one hand, think of public contracts which, for some time now, have provided for the inclusion of the so-called green clauses, which require companies to comply with sustainability standards. In the award of contracts according to the criterion of the most advantageous offer, rather than that of the maximum discount, the importance not only of the economic aspects, but also of those of social and environmental sustainability is highlighted.

Will green contractual clauses apply to all public administration contracts? Between public administrations and with businesses? In this way, all public contract schemes will be colored green, also on a legal level, giving priority to the achievement of green objectives.

The most difficult area of intervention is that of relationships between individuals, both the relationships between business chains and the relationships between businesses and consumers. In these cases, it is discussed which are the best mechanisms to use to have green contracts concluded between private individuals.

The law can intervene authoritatively, depending on the case, by prohibiting or imposing the conclusion of the contract and even the content of some clauses, respectively, black or green. The imposition, however, is based on external limits to the exercise of contractual autonomy, which is normally left to the dialectic of consents, which animates contractual and market freedom.

In this sense, on a voluntary basis, private individuals could conclude contracts with green clauses, but support is needed to guide these choices.

The document from the European Commission talks about allocating funds and granting financial incentives for transition, both for those who are advantaged and for those who can suffer harm.

Communication campaigns are also envisaged to raise awareness of the conclusion of green contracts, both for the supply chains of companies that want to qualify and for consumers who want to contribute to sustainable choices with their purchases, once again overcoming an exclusively economic approach. at least in the short term.

Summary: public and private contracts are the most effective tool for implementing green policies in the various sectors involved in the transformation processes. The conclusion of green contracts must be encouraged, as it must pass an assessment of short-term economic convenience. The contractual choice of businesses and citizens is essential to achieve the objectives of the new green economy.

3. Management of the conflict related to the transition to the green economy

The third phase concerns the management of the conflict related to the transition to the green economy.

The transition process, above all, if imposed with the tight deadlines indicated in the Commission's plan, will cause strong conflicts and serious conflicts. These are epochal changes that affect all economic sectors and involve significant shifts in the organization of production processes.

The Commission assumes the double lever of imposition and sharing, but the onset of conflicts is foreseeable that must be managed efficiently, in order to ensure the achievement of the objectives. In hypothesizing appropriate financing to support investments in the new green economy and for compensatory measures for the injured, once again, a consensual compositional path is indicated that tends to be inclusive.

The judicial, European or state authoritative resolution of conflicts is accompanied by an amicable settlement achieved through compositional and conciliatory agreements. This second path is to be preferred, not only because it is simpler and faster, but also because it allows to find shared solutions that guarantee economic and social cohesion.

In this sense, the conciliation and mediation mechanisms, which already have a common European discipline, can usefully be used also for the amicable resolution of conflicts linked to the green transition.

Without prejudice to the inalienability of the fundamental right to judicial protection, the use of out-of-court settlement solutions can be imposed by law, by the judge or agreed by the parties to the conflict. To facilitate the effective use of mediation, it is necessary to check whether to leave access left to the voluntary nature of the parties or whether to legally impose it.

Summary: the conciliatory agreement must be the main tool for resolving conflicts triggered by the implementation of green policy. Access to consensual resolution mechanisms must be encouraged because it is essential for inclusion.

4. Conclusions

To plan, implement and manage the policy of the new green economy, two levers are available, respectively, focused on the authoritative-taxing approach and the voluntary-sharing approach.

Since the approval of the European policy, therefore, it is necessary to make precise choices of authoritative or consensual sense, in identifying the legal sources, the implementation tools and the most appropriate compositional mechanisms.

The compulsory – voluntary alternative could be overcome through the assumption of social responsibility by institutions and administrations, in the public sphere, and by businesses and citizens / consumers, in the private sphere.

With the social responsibility for the realization of the new green economy, in fact, without being forced, institutions, administrations, businesses and citizens voluntarily undertake a binding commitment to achieve the objectives of the new green deal, because they are convinced of its usefulness in the interest general all and of the next generations.

Contractual autonomy, at different levels, is colored green and blue for a transition that overcomes a selfish and patrimonial approach typical of the civil law tradition.